

Existence of Foreign Language Anxiety in Major and Non-Major English Graduates of South Punjab

Iram Sharif¹, Asia Iqbal², Muhammad Shafiq³, Anila Shakil⁴

Abstract

Foreign language anxiety could be a hurdle in gaining the advanced knowledge and the communicative competencies. Graduate students have to go through the phases of national and international development through their development skills. The English language is an essential key of communication and advanced knowledge skills. Graduate students cannot perform better, if they have foreign language anxiety. Present study is conducted to understand the comparatively, existence of foreign language anxiety in major and non-major English graduate students studying in the institutes of Southern Punjab. Foreign Language Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) by Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope (1986) is adopted to measure the anxiety of the graduate students. This scale consists of 33 different questions while the data is collected from the sample of 200 graduate students studying in different institutes of Southern Punjab. Obtained data is analyzed in SPSS version 25 and tabulation is made in Microsoft Excel 2016. The results of the study show that there is an existence of foreign language anxiety in graduate students. Comparatively, male students are more prey of anxiety as compared to females. The results also show that, even non-major English students have anxiety, but they are seemed to be more willing and motivated to learning English as a foreign language, compared to major English graduate students.

Keywords: Language Anxiety, EFL, Motivation, Graduate Student

1. Introduction

English is spoken in more than 100 nations and is the official language of 85% of international organizations. It is also used on all seven continents (David Crystal: 2003). Following the British as traders of the East India Company in 1600, English people entered Pakistan. After winning control, this corporation governed the whole sub-continent in 1858. English replaced other languages on the subcontinent as the official administrative and educational language from 1765 to 1947, when the British Raj was in power. A document by Thomas Macaulay from 1835 that suggested an English educational system for India is widely regarded as a pivotal moment. Following the founding of the universities in Bombay, Calcutta, and Madras in 1857, English replaced other languages as the main medium of instruction (David Crystal, 2003).

It is a recognized official language of Pakistan. Although it does not have a formal standing in the other South Asian nations, it has been the main means of communication between nations throughout the whole rule. It is spoken as a second language in Pakistan. Although it is now considered a second language in Pakistan, it nevertheless has a greater relevance than any other language on the continent. English Language is taught as the compulsory subject in Pakistan from primary to the Graduation level in Pakistan. Since the language has to be learned, the attitude and the linguistic anxiety is being seen towards the English language as the foreign language. The rules and the grammatical structures are diverse to the native language but English language having the official status in Pakistan has to be learned very intentionally. South Punjab is an educationally developing area of Pakistan where most natives have Pashtu as their mother tongue and have to learn English as foreign language after acquisition of Urdu language as the second language.

Foreign Language anxiety can be defined as the worry, frustration issue and negative emotions that are aroused when a learner has to learn a second language other than their mother tongue. The most influencing of learning a foreign language is foreign language anxiety, which is based on the classroom practicing, beliefs about the language and the uniqueness of the language (Horwitz and Cope: 1986). Price (1991) says that a number of students almost have high language anxiety which leads towards the negative effects on learning and performance. Since it is observed that there are English medium courses taught in university, the English language anxiety may lead towards lower language achievement and performance in other subjects as well. South Punjab is known as the developing area of Punjab province of Pakistan where mostly Saraiki language is used as the mother tongue. English is learned and used as the foreign language in the region. Present study is conducted to understand the anxiety level in the graduate students studying in different institutes of Multan which is taken as the sample of the study.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The lower language anxiety can lead towards the higher language acquisition process at graduate level in the presence of proper motivation and classroom activities.

1.2. Significance of the Study

The current study will help to understand the anxiety level among students and will propose possible solutions to decrease the foreign language anxiety for better language learning outcomes.

1.3. Objectives

- To determine the levels of (English language learning) anxiety in EFL learners at graduate level

¹ M.Phil. in English (Applied Linguistics), Minhaj University Lahore, Pakistan

² PhD Scholar, English Linguistics, University of Jamshoro; Senior Lecturer in English Department at Institute of Southern Punjab, Pakistan

³ Associate Professor of English, Department of English, Emerson University Multan, Pakistan

⁴ Corresponding Author: Master of Science in Psychology, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan, Pakistan, Email: aqeelpk786@yahoo.com

- To investigate the impacts of anxiety on English language learning by observing impact on major and non-major English graduate students
- To recommend strategies for minimizing language learning anxiety of EFL learners.

1.4. Research Questions

- What are the factors causing the foreign language anxiety at graduate level in South Punjab?
- What is the impact of foreign language anxiety on major and non-major English graduate students?
- Which strategies can be applied to overcome on the foreign language anxiety at graduate level in South Punjab?

2. Literature Review

Wu (2010) conducted a research study on “*The Relationship between learners’ anxiety and learning strategy in the CLT classroom*”. The purpose of study was to investigate the relationship between language learners’ anxiety and learning strategy. It was included in the aim of study that how students perceive grammar translation method and communicative language approach. To conduct the study foreign language classroom anxiety scale (FLCAS) and communicative language teaching attitude scale. The results showed that the students had a positive attitude towards communicative language approach. The anxiety level can be reduced by effective language learning and language teaching strategy in the classroom. It was also concluded in the study that the teacher would provide awareness and would change language teaching studies from rational to the modern language teaching approaches to reduce the learners ‘anxiety so that there must be an effective learning process in the CLT classroom.

Hismanoglu (2013) investigated on “*Foreign Language Anxiety of English Language Teachers Candidates: A Sample from Turkey*”. FLCAS by Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope (1986) was selected as an instrument to measure the foreign language anxiety. For the purpose of study (132) candidates were selected out of which there were 46 male and 86 female of ELT individuals of ELT department at a state university in turkey the participants were selected randomly of different stages the results of the study showed that there was a low level of foreign language learning anxiety of ELT candidates it was also found that anxiety had significant relationship with independent variables which were gender, age and great level.

Joshi (2015) conducted a study in which the purpose was illustrated to find out the reasons for English language anxiety amongst hotel management students and its impact on their performance. For the purpose of conducting study, 50 students were selected from AISSMS College of Hotel Management. The study revealed that the students of rural background have more anxiety than those in urban areas. The Language anxiety checks students from linguistics speaking competency.

Alswot (2016) made a research study on “*Foreign Language Anxiety in Higher Education: A Practical Framework for Reducing FLA*”. The purpose of the study was to investigate the measure of the anxiety level among the graduate students of Taif University in Saudi context. The instruments for investigation were two questionnaires out of which one was a modified version of Foreign Language Anxiety Scale (FLCAS by Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope: 1986) and the other was Inventory of Foreign Language Acquisition Factor. A sample of 373 was selected out of which 205 were male and 168 were female English language learners. The study was quantitative by method. The results of the study revealed that the main causes of speaking anxiety were the pronunciation, questioning fear of mistakes and the negative evaluation of EFL. The study also revealed that speaking English was the main reason for language anxiety.

Debrely & Demirkan (2016) conducted a research study ‘*Sources and levels of foreign language speaking anxiety of English as a foreign language university language learners with regard to language proficiency and gender*’. The objectives behind the study was to investigate the speaking anxiety causes and the sources which make the students anxious to conduct the study the sample of 196 Turkish and Turkish Cypriot language learners were selected by teachers were the main reasons of anxiety it was also found by the study that no understanding of questions raised by teachers is also a big reason behind English language anxiety.

Pei-xin (2016) made a research study on ‘*An Analysis of English learners’ Anxiety and Coping Strategies in China*’. The purpose of the study was to investigate the reason behind language anxiety in china students. The study revealed that the anxiety which is presented because of least opportunities, teacher centered and old ideas of learning.

3. Research Methodology

The present study is descriptive by approach and quantitative in its nature. Gay (2012) defines quantitative study as the study which provides numeric description of the facts and figures through graphs and tables.

3.1. Design of the Study

The present study is purely quantitative in its nature by adopting the Foreign Language Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) by Howrwtiz, Horwitz and Cope (1986) which is helpful in measuring the anxiety level among students. By using five likert scales of “Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree”, the significance of the data tends to be manipulated. For the analysis of the data, SPSS 25 version is used while tabulation is further made through Microsoft Excel 2016.

3.2. Theoretical Framework

The study is being conducted on the proposed language anxiety measurement questionnaire Foreign Language Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) by Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope (1986) through which the significance of the data is measured to check the range of anxiety among students of South Punjab .

The questionnaire consisted of the language anxiety measurement scale, manipulating the anxiety level among students in South Punjab where English language is being taught as the foreign language. Three of the universities are selected as the sample of the study while the data is collected with convenient sampling. The study highlights the presence of language anxiety among students and is able to propose the suggestions to remove it. Five likert scale is the best tool to measure the significance of the problem. The significance level will be described in mean value that will illustrate the significance if the value will be higher than 2.5.

3.3. Population

The population of the current study is South Punjab which is located in the west side in the map of Pakistan.

3.4. Sampling

To complete the study, a sample of three institutes of South Punjab are selected. The sample of the study is 200 students studying in three different institutes.

Following institutes are selected as the sample of the study:

- Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan
- University of Education Lahore (Multan Campus)
- Institute of Southern Punjab Multan

3.5. Data Collection

Instruments for data collection

For finding the levels of anxiety in learners Horwitz (1983) Likert scale and the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) is used. It is a questionnaire consisting of 33 items in a 5-point Likert scale that range from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree”.

In order to explore how English language learning is affected by anxiety; the researcher will devise spoken and written activities such as language games, debates, and open-ended interviews for the learners.

4. Data Analysis

Table 1: Data Analysis

Q.	Statement of the Question	Male						Female				
		Major English		Non-Major English		Total		Major English		Non-Major English		Total
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean
1	<i>I am never quite sure of myself when I am speaking in English.</i>	3.53	0.97	3.37	1.07	3.47	1.00	3.27	1.10	3.50	0.92	3.38
2	<i>I am afraid of making mistakes in English classes.</i>	3.07	1.08	2.79	1.23	2.96	1.14	2.82	1.01	2.79	0.88	2.80
3	<i>I tremble when I know that I am going to be called on in English classes.</i>	2.63	1.25	2.42	1.39	2.55	1.29	2.33	1.08	2.21	1.13	2.28
4	<i>I get frightened when I do not understand what the teacher is saying in English.</i>	3.00	1.11	3.37	1.01	3.14	1.08	2.85	1.09	3.00	1.05	2.92
5	<i>It would not bother me at all to take more English classes.</i>	3.07	1.05	3.26	1.15	3.14	1.08	2.97	1.16	3.07	1.21	3.02
6	<i>During English class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the course.</i>	3.10	1.12	2.74	1.28	2.96	1.19	2.97	1.13	3.32	1.12	3.13
7	<i>I always feel that the other students speak English better than I do.</i>	3.60	0.93	3.84	0.76	3.69	0.87	3.33	1.11	3.36	1.34	3.34
8	<i>I am usually at ease during tests in my class.</i>	3.53	1.14	3.47	1.22	3.51	1.16	3.39	1.30	3.36	1.28	3.38
9	<i>I start panic when I have to speak without preparation in English classes.</i>	3.00	1.34	3.26	1.56	3.10	1.42	3.06	1.41	3.18	1.25	3.11
10	<i>I get nervous and confused when I am speaking in English classes.</i>	3.30	1.18	3.21	1.13	3.27	1.15	2.91	1.13	2.86	0.97	2.89
11	<i>I do not understand why some people get so upset over English class.</i>	3.23	0.94	3.68	1.00	3.41	0.98	3.27	1.21	3.07	1.12	3.18
12	<i>In English class, I can get so nervous that I forget things I know.</i>	3.70	0.88	3.26	1.15	3.53	1.00	2.94	1.22	3.21	1.20	3.07
13	<i>I get embarrassed to volunteer answers in English classes.</i>	3.50	1.17	3.05	1.13	3.33	1.16	3.09	1.26	3.04	1.07	3.07
14	<i>I feel nervous while speaking English with native speakers.</i>	3.50	1.11	3.05	1.18	3.33	1.14	3.00	1.32	2.86	1.48	2.93
15	<i>I get upset when I do not understand what the teacher is correcting.</i>	3.30	1.12	3.47	1.22	3.37	1.15	3.15	1.12	3.11	0.92	3.13
16	<i>Even If I am well prepared for English class, I feel</i>	2.80	1.16	2.79	1.18	2.80	1.15	2.52	0.94	2.86	1.11	2.67

Q.	Statement of the Question	Male						Female				
		Major English		Non-Major English		Total		Major English		Non-Major English		Total
		Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D	Mean
	<i>anxious about it.</i>											
17	<i>I often feel like not going to my English class.</i>	3.03	1.10	3.26	1.05	3.12	1.07	2.45	1.12	2.64	1.03	2.54
18	<i>I do not feel confident when I speak English in classes.</i>	3.07	1.17	3.21	1.23	3.12	1.18	2.52	1.23	2.79	1.07	2.64
19	<i>I am afraid that my English teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make.</i>	3.37	1.07	3.26	1.24	3.33	1.13	2.88	1.19	3.29	1.30	3.07
20	<i>I can feel my heart pounding when I am going to be called on in English classes.</i>	3.07	1.11	3.37	1.01	3.18	1.07	2.94	1.30	2.96	1.14	2.95
21	<i>The more I study for an English test, the more confused I get.</i>	3.40	0.81	3.47	1.07	3.43	0.91	3.33	1.22	3.07	1.30	3.21
22	<i>I do not feel pressure to prepare very well for English class.</i>	3.10	1.09	3.47	0.96	3.24	1.05	3.39	1.09	3.32	1.22	3.36
23	<i>I always feel that the other students speak English better than I do.</i>	3.27	1.01	3.42	1.17	3.33	1.07	3.39	1.03	3.54	1.23	3.46
24	<i>I feel very self-conscious about speaking English in front of other students.</i>	3.37	0.96	2.89	1.05	3.18	1.01	3.06	1.03	3.04	1.26	3.05
25	<i>English class moves so quickly that I worry about getting left behind.</i>	2.97	1.16	3.11	1.10	3.02	1.13	2.91	1.26	3.00	1.19	2.95
26	<i>I feel more tense and nervous in my English class than in my other classes.</i>	3.07	1.28	3.11	1.10	3.08	1.20	2.85	1.15	3.11	1.17	2.97
27	<i>I get nervous and confused when I am speaking in my English class.</i>	3.63	1.03	2.79	1.27	3.31	1.19	3.45	1.03	3.43	1.37	3.44
28	<i>When I am on my way to English class, I feel very sure and relaxed.</i>	3.10	1.09	2.95	1.18	3.04	1.12	2.97	1.10	2.75	1.29	2.87
29	<i>I get nervous when I do not understand every word the English teacher says.</i>	3.67	0.96	3.53	0.96	3.61	0.95	3.52	1.06	3.39	1.20	3.46
30	<i>I feel overwhelmed by the number of rules I have to learn to speak English.</i>	3.20	1.16	3.05	1.03	3.14	1.10	2.88	1.22	3.25	1.04	3.05
31	<i>I am afraid that the other students will laugh at me when I speak English.</i>	3.27	1.01	3.16	0.76	3.22	0.92	2.94	1.14	3.11	1.07	3.02
32	<i>I would probably feel comfortable around native speakers of English.</i>	3.03	0.93	3.58	1.07	3.24	1.01	3.30	1.02	3.07	1.39	3.20
33	<i>I get nervous when the English teacher asks questions which I have not prepared in advance.</i>	3.30	0.95	3.11	1.05	3.22	0.98	2.76	1.00	2.96	0.92	2.85

Question No. 1

Basically, the questionnaire is about foreign language anxiety of graduate students. The researcher asks the questions from different male and female graduate students. This question is about the confidence of students to be sure or not, while speaking English. The mean value of major English students is 3.53 and non-major English students have 3.37 mean value, the students with major English have more value, which shows they have more anxiety level in English. Whereas, the table shows that major English female students have 3.27 mean value and non-major female students have 3.50, which shows non-major English female students have less anxiety. It can also be seen that male have 3.47, whereas females have 3.38 mean values in total. Male have more anxiety levels because of social pressure and other circumstances.

Question No.2

This question is about students' fear of making mistakes during the class. The table shows that major English male students have 3.07 and non-major English male students have 2.79, this shows that non-major English is a cause of decreasing the anxiety of male. It also has been mentioned that the female major English students have 2.82 and non-major female students have 2.79 mean value which describes that English female students have more anxiety because of culture and system. The total mean value of male is 2.96, whereas female's mean value is 2.80, this shows females have less anxiety level. Usually they are more confident than male for language use.

Question No. 3

The question is about the trembling feeling of students going to English classes. It can be seen in the table that male major English students have 2.63 and non-major English male students have 2.42 mean value. It also has been shown that female major English students have 2.33 and non-major English female students have 2.21 mean value. Females with a major of English feel more anxiety to go to their English class. It also has been depicted that the total mean value of males is 2.55 and females' total mean

value is 2.28. The overall mean values say that males have more anxiety issues than the females. It's because of the social responsibilities of men in their life, and the other thing is English phobia in males.

Question No. 4

This question is about the fear of a student because he/ she does not understand the teacher during the class. It can be seen that the male major English students have 3.00 mean value, but the male non-major English students have 3.37 mean value, which means that non-major English male students have more levels of fear and anxiety when they do not understand the teachers in their classes. Whereas, it also has been shown in the table that female English major students have 2.85 mean but, female non-major English students have 3.00 mean value, which shows that non-major English female students have more level of fear and anxiety during their class in front of the teacher. It also can be seen that the overall mean value of males is 3.14, whereas, the value of females is 2.92. The overall mean values express that male have more anxiety and fear to attend the class at their graduate level. This can be because of less opportunities and lack of interest in learning as well.

Question No. 5

This question is about the interest of the student to take the English class. The students' responses have been shown in the table. It has been mentioned in the table that male major English students have 3.07 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.26. Male non-major English students have more anxiety to attend the English classes at graduate level. It also has been mentioned that the mean value of female major English students is 2.97, whereas, the female non-major English students have 3.07 mean value, which means that non-major English female students have a greater level of stress and anxiety in taking the English classes at their graduate level. The overall mean value of male is 3.14 and females' total mean value is 3.02, these values depict that male students face more fear and anxiety to attend the English classes. It is because of males' family background and exposure.

Question No. 6

This question is about the understanding of things which do not have any relevance with the course during the study. The table shows that male with major English have 3.10 mean value but male with non-major English students have 2.74 mean value. These values show that English students have more concerns about the content which they study during their class. The female major English students have 2.97 and non-major English female students have 3.32 mean value, which shows that non-major English female students think more about the course during their class. The overall mean value of male is 2.96, whereas females' mean value is 3.13. These given values show that female students usually think more about the things which are not beneficial for students after doing them.

Question No. 7

This question is about spoken English. Few students think that others are better than them in spoken English. The show says that male major English students' mean value is 3.60 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.84, which shows that non-major male students think more about their spoken English than the male major English students. The table portrays that female major English students' mean value is 3.33 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.36, which shows that non-major English female students think that their spoken English is not better than the other graduate students. The male students' total mean value is 3.69 and females' mean value is 3.34. These values show that female major English students think that their spoken English is not better than the others, it can be because of exposure and environment.

Question No. 8

This asked question to the students is about to feel ease during the test. Different students give their responses in their own way. The table shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.53 and non-major male students' mean value is 3.47, which means that major English male students feel more ease in the test than the other graduate students. The table also depicts that female major English students' mean value is 3.39 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.36 which means that major English students feel more ease in the test than the other female students. It also has been mentioned in the table that males' total mean value is 3.51 and females' total mean value is 3.38 which shows that the maximum number of male students feel easier in the test than the females.

Question No.9

This question says that few students feel panic to speak English without preparation in English class. Different students' views have been mentioned in the table. The male major English students' mean value is 3.00 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.26, these values show that non-major male students have a feeling of panic more than the other graduate students. Whereas, female major English male students' mean value is 3.06 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.18 which shows that non-major English female students have more anxiety and feeling of panic to speak English without preparation. Total mean value of male is 3.10 and females' mean value is 3.11, which means that female graduate students have more anxiety and panic feeling than males. This can be because of the environment and exposure.

Question No. 10

This question is about those who feel confused and nervous in the class when they speak English in the class. It can be seen that the mean value of male major English students is 3.30 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.21. This means that male with a major in English are more nervous than the others. Whereas, the female major English students' mean value is 2.91 and non-major English female students' mean value is 2.86. It means that major English females are more nervous and confused in English

classes. Overall mean value of males is 3.27 and females' mean value is 2.89. These given values show that males are more nervous and excited in their English class than females, because they have less time to study their subjects.

Question No. 11

It's about a psychological matter of some students, they get upset in their English class. Different responses have been shown in the table, the male major English students' mean value is 3.23 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.68, which highlights that non-major English male are more disturbed and upset in their English because of lack of confidence. The table shows that female major English students' mean value is 3.27 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.07, which means that females with major English graduates have more fear in the English classes. The total mean value of male is 3.41 and females 'total mean value is 3.18. These given values show that male have more levels of stress and anxiety in their English class because of lack of confidence and exposure.

Question No. 12.

This question is about those students who forget things in English class because they feel nervous. The table portrays that male major English students have 3.70 mean value and non-major English male students have 3.26 mean value, these values in comparison show that major English male students have a habit to forget things because of nervousness. The female major English students' mean value is 2.94, whereas, the female non-major English students have 3.21 mean value, which shows a clear difference that non-major English female students are facing more fear in their English class. The total mean value of male and female is 3.53 and 3.07. This means that male students feel more nervous than the female graduate students because of their less interest in the class.

Question No. 13

This question is about those students who feel embarrassed to volunteer at answers in their English classes, because of lack of confidence and experience. These responses have been shown in the table which explain that male major English graduates have 3.50 mean value whereas non-major English male graduates have 3.05 mean value. This difference conveys a message that male graduates with a major in English feel more embarrassed than the others. The female major English graduates' mean value is 3.09 and non-major English female graduates' mean value is 3.04, both have a very short difference, but female major English graduates get more embarrassed than the others. The total mean value of male and female is 3.33 and 3.07, these values make the difference that male feel more embarrassed than females because of lack of confidence and communication skills.

Question No. 14

It's question is about those students who feel nervous while speaking English with native speakers. Different responses show that male major English students' mean value is 3.50 and male non-major English graduates' mean value is 3.05, these values show that English major male students feel more nervous than the others. Whereas, the mean value of female major English students is 3.00 and female non-major English students' mean value is 2.86. Both of the values show that female major English graduates' feel more nervous to speak with native speakers. The overall mean value of male and female is 3.33 and 2.93, this mentioned difference is because of lack of confidence and communication skills.

Question No. 15

A couple of times, the students do not understand what the teacher is correcting because of less knowledge of the subject. The responses of the students have been mentioned in the table which shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.30 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.47, this difference shows that non-major male students do not understand the teachers that what the teacher is correcting. Whereas, the female major English students have 3.15 mean value and non-major English female graduates mean value is 3.11, it means that female major English graduates do not understand what the teacher is correcting. The total mean value of male is 3.37 and females' mean value is 3.13. These given values show that most of the male students have a problem that they do not understand when they're corrected.

Question No. 16

Even a student is well prepared, but still feels anxious about it, this can be because of lack of confidence. The answers of the students show that male major English students have 2.80 mean value and male non-major English students' mean value is 2.79. Whereas, the mean value of female major English students is 2.52 and female non-major English students have 2.86 mean value. This means that major English female students feel more anxious than the others. The overall mean value of male is 2.80 and females' mean value is 2.67, which means that male are more anxious for their English class. This is because of hesitation and lack of confidence.

Question No. 17

This question is about the students who often like not going to English class. The table describes that male major English students' mean value is 3.03 and non-major male English students' mean value is 3.26, it means that non-major male students often do not go for their English class, this can be because of lack of interest for the class. It also can be seen that female major English students' mean value is 2.45 and non-major English students have 2.64 mean value, the values show that non-major English students often do not go for their English class. The total mean value of male is 3.12 and females' total mean value is 2.54, it means that male often do not go for their English class because of lack of interest.

Question No. 18

A couple of students have a problem speaking in front of class because they have a lack of confidence and they feel hesitant. The researcher asks that students do not feel confident when they speak English in the class. The responses of the students show that male major English students' mean value is 3.07 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.21, it means major English students have more problems of confidence in front of class. This also can be seen in the table that female major English students' mean value is 2.52 and non-major English female students' mean value is 2.79, this depicts that non-major English females have more problems of confidence during the class. It can also be seen that the total mean value of male is 3.12 and females' mean value is 2.64. It means that male are facing more confidence issues than females.

Question No. 19

This question is basically about the fear of students that the teacher is always ready to correct every mistake. The table explains that male major English students' mean value is 3.37 and female non-major students' mean value is 3.26. This difference shows that major English males are more afraid to teacher' correction. The researcher analyzes that female major English students' mean value is 2.88 and non-major English female students' mean value is 3.29. It means that non-major English females are more afraid of teacher' correction. The total mean value of males is 3.33 and females' mean value is 3.07. The difference shows that males overall feel more afraid of their correction.

Question No. 20

This question is about those students who feel heart pounding when they are called for English class, this can be because of fear and anxiety to face the people. The table shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.07 and non-major male English students' mean value is 3.37, which means that non-major male students feel more anxiety and stress to face the English class than the other students. Whereas, female major English students' mean value is 2.94 and non-major English female students' mean value is 2.96. The overall mean value of males is 3.18 and females' mean value is 2.94, these values show that males feel more heart pounding than the females, it is because of lack of confidence and interest.

Question No. 21

The question' statement shows that few students feel that the more they study, the more they get confused. Table describes various answers of the graduate students. The male major English graduates' mean value is 3.40 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.47, which means that non-major graduates have more anxiety and problems of confusion. The table also depicts that female major English students' mean value is 3.33 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.07, it means major English students feel confusion in their studies. The total mean value of males is 3.43 and females' total mean value is 3.21, both of the values say that males graduates face confusion more than the females. It is because of lack of opportunities and lack of interest.

Analysis. 22

Basically, this statement is about those students who do not feel pressure while they prepare for their English class. The given table shows that the male major English graduates' mean value is 3.10 and male non-major English students' mean value is 3.47, these values say that non-major male graduates do not feel pressure to prepare for English class. It also has been mentioned that female major English students' mean value is 3.39 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.32, this shows that female major English graduates do not get the pressure of English class. It can be seen that the total males mean value is 3.24 and females' total mean value is 3.36. Female students are more confident, they do not get pressured by English class. Females are more confident and have the communication ability to come with others.

Question No. 23

This question is about those who think that other graduate students speak better than he/ she. The researcher takes the response of different students. The table shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.27 and male non-major English graduates' mean value is 3.42, the non-major students think that others speak English better. It is also mentioned in the table that female major English students' mean value is 3.39 and female non-major English students' mean value is 3.54, which means that non-major students face this problem and that their spoken English is not better than others. The total mean value of males is 3.33 and females' total mean value is 3.46. These given values show that male graduates' students think that their spoken English is not better than the females, this means that they have lack of confidence and interest.

Question No. 24

This question is about those students who feel self-conscious, when they speak English in front of class. The students gave their different points of views which are mentioned in the table. The table shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.37 and male non-major English students' mean value is 2.89 which shows that major English male students are more self-conscious when they face their English class. Whereas, major English female students' mean value is 3.06 and non-major females' mean value is 3.04, these values tell us that major English female students are more self-conscious than the others. It has been mentioned that the total mean value of males is 3.18 and females' total mean value is 3.05, this tells us that males feel more self-conscious than the females in their English class. This can be because of the exposure and environment of males.

Question No. 25

It has been seen that students think that English class moves fast, they are left behind it. The question is about students' speed with English class. The table describes that male major English students' mean value is 2.97 and male non-major English students' mean

value is 3.11. These given values show that male major English students think that they have been left behind by other students. The female major English students' mean value is 2.91 and non-major students' mean value is 3.00, it means that major female students think that they left behind the English class. It also can be seen that the total mean value of males is 3.02 and females' total mean value is 2.95, this means that male students are left behind as they think.

Question No.26

Most of the students feel more nervous in English class than the other classes, it is because of stress, lack of interest and lack of background knowledge. It has been seen in the table that the male major English students' mean value is 3.07 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.11. This means that non-major English students feel more nervous than the others. The table shows that major English female students' mean value is 2.85 and non-major female English students' mean value is 3.11, these values depict that non-major student's face and feel more nervous. It also has been mentioned that the males total mean value is 3.08 and females' total mean value is 2.97. Both of these values show that male students are more nervous in their English class than the females.

Question No. 27

The researcher asks this question about the student who gets confused and nervous in front of class when he/ she speaks English. The table says that male major English students' mean value is 3.63 and male' non-major English value is 2.79, these values show that male major English students get more confused and nervous. Whereas, the female major English students' mean value is 3.45 and non-major English female students' mean value is 3.43, which means that major English students feel more nervous and confused. The total mean value of males is 3.31 whereas, the females' total mean value is 3.44. These values show that females have a more problem of confusion and feel nervous.

Question No. 28

When a student is on the way to English class, they feel relaxed, this is because of the student's interest. Its responses have been shown in the table, the table shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.10 and non-major English students' mean value is 2.95, both of the values show that male major English students feel good and relaxed as they go for their English class. Whereas, the female major English students' mean value is 2.97 and female non-major English students' mean value is 2.75. It means that females' major students are more confident and feel relaxed going to their English class. The total mean value of males is 3.61 and females' total mean value is 3.46, which means that males are more relaxed to go for their English class.

Question No. 29

Few of the students get confused because they do not understand their English teacher' words. The given table shows the responses of the students, the male major English students' mean value is 3.67 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.53, which shows that more of the male major English students do not understand their teacher's words than the others. The table also depicts that female major English students' mean value is 3.52 and non-major English female students' mean value is 3.39, it means that female major English students feel that they do not understand them very well. The total mean value of males is 3.61 and females' mean value is 3.46. These values show that males get more confused about their teacher' words because they do not understand the words very well.

Question No. 30

It has been seen that most of the time a couple of students feel overwhelmed as they learn a number of rules of English to learn. The table shows difficult values for students' answers. The male major English students' mean value is 3.20 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.05, which means that major English male students feel more overwhelmed as they have to learn a number of English rules. Whereas, female major English students' mean value is 2.88 and non-major English female students' mean value is 3.25, it means that non-major English females are more overwhelmed in learning English rules than the other females. It can also be seen that the total mean value of males is 3.14 and females' total mean value is 3.05. It can be seen that males feel more overwhelmed than females in learning the English rules. It can be because of the lack of interest of the male students

Question No. 31

The given statement shows that few of the students feel shy because of lack of confidence. They think that others will laugh at him/ her when he/ she speaks in front of the class. The researcher took different answers from students, the table shows that male major English students' mean value is 3.27 and the non-major male English students' mean value is 3.16, these values show that male major English students feel more nervous and think that others will laugh at them if they speak English in front of them. The table also shows that females' major English students mean value is 2.94 and non-major English female students mean value is 3.11, these given values show that non-major English female students feel more shy and they think that others will laugh at them if they speak. The total mean value of males is 3.22 and females mean value is 3.02.

Question No. 32

As a researcher, it has been observed that few of the motivated, dedicated and confident students are comfortable around native English speakers, because they want to speak like a native. The shown table depicts that male major English students' mean value is 3.03 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.58, it means that non-major male students feel more comfortable with the native speaker than the others. Whereas, the female major English graduates' mean value is 3.30 and non-major English female graduates' mean value is 3.07, which means that female major English students are more comfortable with native speakers. The

table shows that the total mean value of male students is 3.24 and female students mean 3.20, this difference shows that male students are more comfortable with native speakers.

Question No. 33

It has been observed that few of the students feel nervous when they are given a surprise test or asked questions suddenly without preparation. The table shows the answers of the students, it can be seen that male major English students' mean value is 3.30 and non-major English male students' mean value is 3.11, which shows that major English male students get nervous as they are asked for a surprise test. Whereas, major English female students' mean value is 2.76 and non-major English female students' mean value is 2.96, this difference shows that non-major students are more nervous if they are asked the questions surprisingly. The total mean value of males is 3.22 and females' mean value is 2.85, these values show that males are more nervous if they are asked questions surprisingly. Because they do not prepare themselves mentally.

1. Conclusion

It can be concluded that there is the existence of foreign language anxiety in the students of South Punjab. This anxiety is also due to the lack of motivation, environment, teaching and learning strategies and the social pressure. Comparatively, the existence of foreign language anxiety is more in male than in female graduate students. The non-major English students have less anxiety but they seem motivated to gain the foreign language comparatively to the major English students. It can also be said that the use of modern strategies, engagement of the major and non-major students, social distancing removal, drills and trials among the graduate students, the language anxiety can be minimized. Minimization of the foreign language anxiety is the need of graduate students as the students have conducted their projects in English language. New era of modernization, digitalization and globalization give birth to be more confidence based regarding communication skills in English language so there is utmost need of the time and space that the graduate students would have minimum English language anxiety.

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